

**External organic matters for climate mitigation and
soil health**

EOM4Soil

Data Management Plan-V2

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ABSTRACT

This document outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the EJP SOIL Project EOM4Soil and describes the data management approaches adopted for the datasets and metadata collected and generated by the project. This DMP is based upon the H2020 guidelines on FAIR data management and the H2020 open access to research data and scientific publications. It provides information on the purpose, types, formats and origin of research data collected, processed or generated within the project. It defines standards for metadata provision and creation, use of keywords and persistent identifiers, naming conventions and clear versioning. It describes approaches selected for making data openly accessible, interoperable, and reusable. It also covers resources allocated, data security and ethical aspects of EJP SOIL data management. This DMP was submitted on 26^h October 2024.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of abbreviations and acronyms.....	5
1. Datasets management and description	6
1.1. Project EOM4Soil data management	6
1.1.1. Data summary	6
1.1.2. Datasets produced	7
1.1.3. Specific management for each type of data.....	21
1.1.4. FAIR data.....	22
1.1.5. Allocation of resources.....	23
1.1.6. Data security.....	23
1.1.7. Ethical aspects	23
1.1.8. Publications & authorships policy	24

List of abbreviations and acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EJP SOIL	European Joint Programme on agricultural soil management
EOM	External organic matter
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon2020
WP	Work Package

1. Datasets management and description

The datasets described in this section are the research datasets used for scientific publication purpose, directly managed by the EJP SOIL. Internal and external call projects should have their own data management plan, in which they will describe their own datasets and their management. They are invited to use this DMP as a model, since it follows the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP template (designed to be applicable to any Horizon 2020 project that produces, collects or processes research data). The projects may either make sections 1.1 Dataset 1, 1.2 Dataset 2, 1.3 Dataset 3... for each dataset OR describe the whole projects data management together in one section 1.1 Project X data management.

1.1. Project EOM4Soil data management

1.1.1. Data summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) of the EOM4Soil project aims to define key elements that facilitate the possible reuse of all collected and processed data. The EOM4Soil DMP will report: data handling, methodology and standards to be used, data sharing and re-use modalities, archiving and preservation (including storage and backup of project datasets).

Many activities generate organic wastes, including housing and urban activities (e.g. biowastes, sewage sludges and green wastes), industries and agriculture (e.g. manures and fruit surplus). Manures have been traditionally returned to soils, but this is not the case for biowastes, such as food wastes and green wastes, or industrial wastes. The recycling of such external organic matters (EOM) on soils, with or without pre-processing, is strongly encouraged by the Europe Union as part of a Circular Economy. However, such recycling is only possible if soil application is beneficiary for soils and/or crop production. The EOM4Soil project aims to gain knowledge on the use, processing and application of EOM to mitigate climate change, enhance soil quality and maintain crop production with a decrease in use of mineral fertilizer. The structure of the project is summarized in Figure 1. It has 3 blocks of WP concerning:

- EOM production, quantification, characterization (WP1 and WP2)
- EOM application on soil with the assessment of long-term effects (WP3), the C balance and gas emission assessment related with the EOM use in field conditions (WP4) and a focus on contaminants (WP5)
- The cropping systems involving EOMs and the recommendation of best management practices (WP6)

Within EOM4Soil, data have been generated in the achievement of the following project objectives:

- To quantify and denominate the EOMs accessible within the EU to make best use of local resources (WP1, D 1.1).
- To synthesize the characteristics of the EOM types, including indicators of efficiency for C storage in soils and nutrient availability for plants (WP1, D 1.2 and D1.4)
- To define classes of EOMs based on their characteristics and making the link between chemical characteristics, origin of the EOM, process applied and potential benefits or environmental impacts (WP1, D1.6 and D1.7)
- To synthesize the management practices concerning the treatment process before EOM application and improve them (WP2, D 2.1. for anaerobic digestion, D 2.2. for biochar production, D2.3 for composting)
- To synthesize available information concerning the GHG and nutrient emission risks during anaerobic digestion and carbonization processes (D 2.4)
- To collect information and metadata available about medium and long-term trials initiated to assess the effects of repeated applications of EOM on soils (WP3, D 3.1)
- To start additional short-term experiments and new measurements to answer knowledge gaps about the effects of EOM application on soil health, crop production, GHG emission (WP3, D 3.2 and WP4, D 4.4)
- To compare the effects related to the use of different EOMs in crop production through multicriteria analysis and construction of soil and crop quality indices (WP3, D 3.3)
- To synthesize available data in databases about N₂O, NH₃ and VOC emission (WP4, D 4.1) and develop new formalism of emission in models of gas emission (WP4, D 4.2)
- To assess the interactions of EOMs on microbial use efficiency and C stabilisation in soil (WP4, D 4.3)
- To report GHG emission for new EOM (WP4, D 4.4)
- To calculate a GHG budget for different EOMs, including process and application (WP4, D 4.5)
- To synthesize the current limitations of contaminants in EOMs regulated by law and the current contents of contaminants in the participating countries (WP5, D5.1)
- To quantify the contaminants contents in new EOM produced from innovative tested processes in WP2 (WP5, D5.2)
- To improve the knowledge about microplastic contaminations in soils after EOM repeated applications and the phytotoxic effects (WP5, D5.3)
- To assess how innovative process proposed in WP2 modify the toxicity of EOMs (WP5, D5.4)
- To assess and compare the consequences of EOM use in representative arable crop successions in the participating countries using simulation models (WP6, D6.1)
- To define the best management practices for EOM uses for farmers and guidelines for end-users (WP6, D6.2)
- To produce a list of policy recommendations for EOM use by farmers (WP6, D6.4)

1.1.2. Datasets produced

In EOM4Soil, each WP will be responsible for implementing the DMP under the supervision of WP7.

In relation to the specific objectives of EOM4Soil, several datasets will originate from the different WPs activities, in .xlsx and .docx format.

Three types of data are produced within EOM4Soil project :

(i) **TYPE 1 : data already existing collected** for general characterization of EOM, meta-analysis of EOM characteristics (WP1, WP2 and WP5), review of data and meta-data about Long-term field experiments

with repeated EOM applications (WP3 and WP4), data about contaminants contents in EOMs and related regulation (WP5); data describing management practices of crop, cultures and EOM application collected to run the simulated scenario (WP6)

(ii) **TYPE 2 : new experimental data** produced by the partners within the EOM4Soil project to address objectives proposed in the EOM4Soil project (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5) ;

(iii) **TYPE 3 : new data generated from multicriteria analysis** applied on data collected from LTE (WP3) **or simulation** of management practices for EOM application in different contexts either representing actual management practices or scenario of improved management practices (WP6)

(iv) **TYPE 4:** synthesis of surveys, discussions during focus groups (new information), synthesis of existing legislation texts concerning EOM production and use (synthesis of existing information) in WP6

Specifically, the different WPs are expected to generate the following protocols and WP datasets described in the following table:

EOM4SoilDataset name	Institutions in charge	WP	Data summary	FAIR	resources	Data security	Ethic
<p>WP1 – D1.1, D1.2, D1.4, D1.6, D1.7</p>	<p>INRAE, LUKE, CSIC</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>EOM classification based on origin, Process nature, major raw materials.</p> <p>List of denominations based on the previous information</p> <p>Quantities of EOM produced in partners countries.</p> <p>Analytical characteristics of EOM (dry matter content, C, organic N, mineral N, P, K, Mg, Ca, Na, pH, trace elements Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Zn, Hg, PAHs, PCBs</p> <p>Already existing data (Type 1) either from already published database (national inventory for example), produced by the partners</p>	<p>All publications and research data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3) : https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>The costs related to open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the EJP SOIL grant by project partners involved in WP1.</p>		<p>Ethical concerns not expected. Only data about EOM produced in countries will be collected at the country scale and not at personal level.</p>

WP2_dataset	LUKE, U. Palermo	2	<p>Experimental dataset about anaerobic digestion of various mixtures: analysis of input and digestates (TS, VS, C, H, N, S, O, ash, cellulose, hemicellulose, Lignin, Fe, N kjeldhal, NH4-N, P, K, Biomethane production potential), CH4 production, pH and in pilot reactors, C balance during anaerobic digestion, AWEN-extractions of digestate.</p> <p>Yasso-modelling results of digestate.</p> <p>New experimental data about NMR characteristics of EOMs.</p> <p>New experimental data (Type 2)</p>	<p>WP2 publications will be published in Gold or Green Open Access</p> <p>Raw data which is not accessible via the publications will be available on request</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>The costs related to WP2 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.</p>	<p>The WP2 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).</p>	<p>Ethical concerns not expected.</p>
WP2_dataset	LUKE, BOKU		<p>Literature survey data on carbonization processes (D2.2) and the risk for GHG and nutrient emissions from EOM processing (D2.4)</p>	<p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>		<p>The WP2 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply</p>	<p>Ethical concerns not expected.</p>

						with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	
WP3_dataset	CRAW, INRAE,	3-1	<p>Inventory of long-term and medium term field experiments using EOMs existing in Europe: metadata collected (geographical situation, institution, soil type, climatic data, EOM tested, followed parameters :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In soils: physical, chemical, biological properties - For plants: yield, analysed parameters, technical management of crops - For EOM: types, doses, analytical characteristics <p>Already existing data (Type 1)</p>	<p>All publications and research data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3): https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	The costs related to WP3 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.	The WP3 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	Ethical concerns not expected.
WP3_dataset	CSIC, CREA, AGES	3-2	<p>New experimental data (Type 2).</p> <p>New short-term experiments have been started by EOM4Soil partners: CSIC, AGES, CREA.</p>	<p>WP2 publications will be published in Gold or Green Open Access</p> <p>Data will be available on ZENODO EOM4Soil</p>	The costs related to WP3 open access scientific	The WP3 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful	Ethical concerns not expected.

			<p>The information collected concerned:</p> <p>Geographical localization of the experiment, design of the experiment, soil type, climatic information,</p> <p>EOM information (types, doses, analytical characteristics</p> <p>soil analysis (texture, moisture, electrical conductivity, organic and inorganic C, Total N, Ca, Mg, Na, P, K, S, cation exchange capacity, pH), soil respiration, biological indicators (microbial biomass, N-fixing bacteria, actinomycetes, yeasts, aerobes, PLFA analysis), enzymatic activities,</p> <p>crop yield, plant analysis</p>	<p>community (see conditions in 1.1.3): https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.</p>	<p>processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).</p>	
WP3_LTE database	INRAE	3-3	<p>Some of the LTE listed in WP3-1 have been used:</p> <p>Detailed Experimental data have been collected from the contacted partners (from EOM4Soil or not) from one or several cropping seasons including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geographical localization, soil type, climatic condition, crop rotation, residue management, age of the trial - Crop management : crops implanted every year, EOM and mineral fertilizers input (dose and rate) 	<p>All publications and research data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3): https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will</p>	<p>The costs related to WP3 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.</p>	<p>The WP3 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).</p>	<p>Ethical concerns not expected.</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil parameters: Soil fertility parameters (major crop nutrients, pH, oligoelements), soil contaminants (metal trace elements), soil biology (soil biodiversity – micro and macro-organisms, soil enzymatic activity), soil physical properties (soil stability, available soil water content), soil organic matter and soil organic carbon. - EOM physicochemical characterisation : nutrient, oligo- and metallic trace elements content, organic contaminants – variability depending on data partner. EOM type is described according to WP1 EOM arborescence. - Plant parameters : crop yield + nutrient content in crops (major nutrients and oligoelements involved in human physiology) <p>These collected data (type1) were gathered in a dataset used for further statistical analysis to define quality indices (see below: WP3_Multicriteria indices dataset)</p>	<p>be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>			
WP3: Multicriteria indices dataset	INRAE	3-3	<p>Type 3 data : data generated from multicriteria analysis. (new data from statistical analysis of already existing data)</p> <p>Global dataset : For each LTE, each treatment and each replicate collected,</p>	<p>The multicriteria indices dataset will be released as supplementary materials for the associated scientific article.</p>	<p>The costs related to WP3 open access scientific publications</p>	<p>The WP3 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including</p>	<p>Ethical concerns not expected.</p>

			<p>multicriteria indices on soil quality are computed. The data will contain the following columns :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Site, treatment and replicate identifying information - Soil or plant variable name (see WP3 – LTE dataset for soil and plant parameter description) - Measured value for the parameter, normalized indicator, weighted indicator and quality. These 4 columns represent the steps of the analysis. <p>Individual analysis reports : For each LTE and each variable category, an analysis report is produced, containing the raw data, normalized data and statistical functions used for normalisation, weighted data and intermediary steps for calculation of the weighing factors. One xlsx file for each LTE and each time series, each xlsx file containing one sheet per variable category.</p>	<p>All data will be saved in .xlsx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types.</p> <p>Dataset will be described in the scientific article, giving readers all the necessary metadata and a DOI, in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>has been claimed as part of the project budget.</p>	<p>against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).</p>	
WP4_dataset	INRAE	4-1.1	<p>Dataset of existing data produced by partners (N2O, NH3) or collected from literature (VOC)</p> <p>Already existing information and Data (type 1)</p>	<p>All publications will be published in Gold or Green Open Access</p> <p>Experimental collected Data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3): https://zenodo.org/com</p>	<p>The costs related to WP4 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the</p>	<p>The WP4 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of</p>	<p>Ethical concerns not expected.</p>

				<p>munities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>Data collected from the literature (VOC) will be available on demand</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	project budget.	personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	
WP4_dataset	BOKU, CREA, CSIC	4.1.2	<p>New experimental dataset (Type 2): in field experiment listed in 3.2. additional measurement of N2O and NH3 have been realized.</p> <p>Additional lab experiment have been realized to measure NH3 and N2O emission simultaneously to chemical analysis and biological parameters</p>	<p>All publications will be published in Gold or Green Open Access</p> <p>Data will be available on ZENODO EOM4Soil community: https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion</p>	The costs related to WP4 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.	The WP4 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	Ethical concerns not expected.

				of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.			
WP4_dataset	INRAE, CSIC	4.3	<p>New experimental dataset (Type 2) on CUE :</p> <p>Two short-term laboratory experiments have been performed by EOM4Soil partners: INRAE, CSIC.</p> <p>The information collected concerned:</p> <p>Design of the experiment, basic soil properties of the tested soil, basic properties of the applied EOM, soil respiration, microbial biomass carbon, microbial DNA quantity, microbial CUE</p>	<p>All publications will be published in Gold or Green Open Access</p> <p>Data will be available on request after publication of the scientific paper(s).</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	The costs related to WP4 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.	The WP4 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	Ethical concerns not expected.
WP5_dataset	AGS	5.1	<p>Already existing data collected from the partners (Type 1)</p> <p>Dataset including :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - list of contaminants analysed in EOM (Trace elements, organic contaminants) - available analytical results of contaminant contents in EOM : Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn, As, PAH, PCB, PCDD/F, pharmaceuticals, flame 	<p>All publications and research data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3) : https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p>	The costs related to WP5 open access scientific publications has not been claimed as part of the project budget but will be	The WP5 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply	Ethical concerns not expected.

			retardants, aliphatic hydrocarbons, pesticides) - regulated thresholds for contaminant contents in the different countries	All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.	provided by the scientific unit.	with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	
WP5_dataset	SLU, AGS	5.3	New experimental dataset (Type 2) Quantification of microplastics in EOMs and soils amended with microplastics	All publications have been published in Gold or Green Open Access One dataset on laboratory experiments is freely available at dryad (doi: 10.5061/dryad.x69p8czjv). The second dataset (Field data) will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3) : https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types.	The costs related to WP5 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.	The WP5 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	Ethical concerns not expected.

				Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.			
WP6_dataset	INRAE	6-1	<p>dataSet of Scenario of EOM use under different pedoclimatic condition in different countries (collected information about crop succession, fertilisation practices, EOM application...)</p> <p>Dataset of simulated results from scenario over periods of 30 years: Evolution of soil organic C, mineral fertilizer substitution, GHG budget of scenario....</p> <p>Generation of new dataset after simulation of the scenario of use (Type 3)</p>	<p>All publications and research data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil community (see conditions in 1.1.3) : https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	The costs related to WP6 open access scientific publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.	The WP6 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).	Ethical concerns not expected.
WP6_dataset	CREA	6.2	Focus group on EOM value chain in Italy are bottom-up dialogue among actors of different EOMs value chains, in particular biochar, digestate, manure and compost,	All publications and research data will be published in Gold or Green Open Access repositories: on ZENODO EOM4Soil	The costs related to WP6 open access scientific	The WP6 leader will take appropriate measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful	Ethical concerns not expected. Regarding Focus groups only data and info about EOM produced in

		<p>which has been established, in Italy, in spring 2024 (from January to September). More specifically, focus groups on biochar, digestate, manure and compost production and use have been conducted to gather more realistic knowledge of the EOMs value chains in specific local contexts and, more generally, at national level. The aim is collecting information about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gaps in legislation for EOMs producers and farmers; • environmental sustainability of EOMs use in different contexts (e.g. where relevant: Nitrate Vulnerable Zones - NVZ vs. non-Nitrate Vulnerable Zones – nNVZ, as defined by the European Directive 91/676/CEE); • economic sustainability for EOMs producers and farmers (needs and barriers). <p>Policy - investigating policy barriers hindering the production and the use of EOM’ amendments and policy solutions to overcome the identified barriers.</p> <p>Classification of policy instruments which could contribute to addressing the management of agricultural soil in the EU and Türkiye according to the principle related to the final objective of soil amendments, increase the soil organic</p>	<p>community (see conditions in 1.1.3) : https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types. Following the completion of data collection, datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>publications has been claimed as part of the project budget.</p>	<p>processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access. Protection of personal data comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).</p>	<p>Italy will be collected at the country scale with some comparison at EU level.</p>
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		<p>content. These policy areas are: Incentivising the adoption of sustainable practices; Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development; Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape; Co-creation and sharing of innovation and knowledge; Triggering new market opportunities.</p> <p>Data are of type 4 (surveys, synthesis of discussion)</p>				
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1.1.3. Specific management for each type of data

TYPE 1 : Collected data

The data contributors will be asked if they agree to the use of his/her contributed data set(s) for meta-analysis and review work (not directed to single or few data sets) by adding data to any EOM4Soil data compilation (EOM physico-chemical characterization, metadata about long-term experiments dedicated to the study of EOM application on cropped soils). Those will exclude personal data. Before 2025 the dataset will be shared after curation only within EJP Soil according to the EOM4Soil rules outlined below (zenodo repository).

The compiled data sets from all EOM4Soil data collections will be made open access at the end of the project (January 2025). For non-published data sets that were included in the data collection we will contact the data contributor in December 2024: If the data have not been published yet as part of a paper but the contributor is the data owner, she/he can decide whether the data can be published open access as part of the data compilation or not. If necessary embargo on the access to the repository on zenodo will be provided until publication in a peer review manuscript.

For all EOM4Soil data sets where we aim at publishing data papers, all data contributors will become co-authors. A data contributor is the person named in the database templates as the provider of the dataset and has submitted at least one data set for one site, or one data set about EOM physico-chemical characteristics. This person does not need to be part of the consortium but can be e.g. owners of long-term experiment data, or owners of EOM characterization dataset.

All data contributors are invited to the analysis of the EOM4Soil datasets and to paper writing. Intellectual input to data analysis and paper writing will justify data contributors to become co-authors of the analysis papers. Pure data contribution generally does not justify co-authorships except the data contribution comprises a majority of data used in the analysis. Intellectual input comprises ideas on data analysis and/or their interpretation, writing of paper chapters and/or substantial contribution to improvement and revision of paper drafts. In case of doubt, final judgement will be made by an EOM4Soil steering committee.

TYPES 2 and 3

The new experimental data set produced by the EOM4Soil partners will be open access at the end of the EOM4Soil project (December 2024) if they have already been published or after an embargo period of maximum 2 years (December 2026) defined to make possible the publication of the data by the data producers. The co-authors will be all contributors to the production and interpretation of the data.

For the new simulated data (Type 3), a similar management is proposed. The new simulated data set produced by the EOM4Soil partners will be open access at the end of the EOM4Soil project (December 2024) if they have already been published or after an embargo period of maximum 2 years (December 2026) defined to make possible the publication of the data by the data producers. The co-authors will be all contributors to the production and interpretation of the data (design of the input data : EOM management, cropping practices, scenario of new practices and management, simulation plan, simulated dataset).

Type 4:

The information collected through surveys and during the focus groups (synthesis of regulation texts and legislative frameworks from which depends the EOM processing and applying on soils) produced by the EOM4Soil partners will be open access at the end of the EOM4Soil project (December 2024) if they have already been published or after an embargo period of maximum 2 years (December 2026) defined to make possible the publication of the data by the data producers. The co-authors will be all contributors to the production and interpretation of the data.

All datasets are collected by the partners and made available for sharing and downloading on the Zenodo repository of EOM4Soil. The opensource articles published in EOM4Soil will be periodically uploaded into new the EJPSOIL – INRAE EOM4Soil repository and will be inserted into the ZENODO EOM4Soil one.

1.1.4. FAIR data*Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:*

All datasets will be assigned with a DOI and described with metadata in line with the FAIR principles.

Provisions for metadata will be detailed at a later stage of the project, following the completion of WPs data collection.

Making data openly accessible:

To make EOM4Soil results data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), all publications will be published in Gold or Green Open Access and both publications and research data will be deposited in Open Access repositories, according to EJP SOIL DMP. The costs related to open access scientific publications will be claimed as part of the EJP SOIL grant by each partner. Datasets will be made accessible with OS or compatible commercial statistical programs such as EXCEL, SPSS, etc. According to EJP Soil DMP, T1.2 (WP1) will upload all project datasets to both the CREA and INRAE institutional digital repositories, which have security provisions, services for the creation of machine actionable metadata, long term preservation of data, and all essential characteristic of trusted repositories. Additionally, also the reports D1.3.1, D1.3.2. and D1.3.3., which includes evaluation of project results, will be openly published in the digital repositories for safe store and long-term preservation.

Once datasets and exploitation activities (scientific publications) are completed, the EOM4Soil datasets will be made openly available in the Zenodo repository of the project (https://zenodo.org/communities/ejpsoil_eom4soil/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)

To guarantee the exploitation and publication of data generated in EOM4Soil by the project partners, the EOM4Soil team is asking for an embargo period of 24 months (1st November 2024 -31st October 2026) before opening the generated WP1/2/3/4/5/6 datasets uploaded into the ZENODO_EOM4Soil repository.

EOM4Soil Steering Group

Protection of personal data in the project will be regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

In case of specific restrictions or limitations in the application of sharing data policy by non-EU country participants (in EOM4Soil: TAGEM – Turkey), we will refer to Commission acceptance to keep closed some generated research data. When needed, these restricted datasets will be privately provided after formal request to the beneficiary responsible for datasets generation.

Making data interoperable:

All data will be saved in .xlsx and .docx format, in addition WP4 will use:

- R development Core Team (free use) for statistical analysis
- R and Rshiny scripts needed to run the EOM4SOIL visualisation tool (EOM4SOIL D1.7).

To make data interoperable and allow inter-disciplinary exchanges, standard vocabularies will be used for all data types.

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

To make data re-usable, EOM4Soil will adapt to EJP Soil DMP provisions in terms of data licenses, eventual access restrictions, IP/data ownership policy.

1.1.5. Allocation of resources

In EOM4Soil, WP7 will coordinate and monitor data management activities. WP7, in cooperation with all other WP Leaders, is responsible for the development and monitoring of the adherence to the EJP Soil DMP. EOM4Soil WP leaders are responsible for providing input for the DMP revisions, and for the implementation of the data management policy in their respective WPs.

Each WP/task leader is responsible for building the generated datasets and describing the data originated from WP/task activities, in accordance to present DMP.

1.1.6. Data security

EOM4Soil working data are stored by the partners until the end of the project activities.

WP leaders are responsible for the data they will collect and process, and of previously collected data (re-use of previous datasets) that they might receive. WP7 and WP leaders will take appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure the protection of data against unlawful processing, including against loss, unlawful or accidental elimination, and against unauthorized access.

For all other matters regarding data security, confidentiality and integrity, the project will adhere to EJP Soil DMP provisions.

1.1.7. Ethical aspects

The EOM4Soil coordinator will oversee that the research project will be carried out in accordance with the EJP SOIL DMP provisions and the European Union and respective national requirements regarding ethical aspects. EOM4Soil is not expected to raise significant ethical concerns.

Humans and personal data: EOM4Soil research activities will not involve human participants, personal data collection and/or processing.

Animals: EOM4Soil research activities will not involve animal manipulation or collection.

Third countries: Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM, Turkey) is involved in EOM4Soil as Third Country (Beneficiary n. 25): this is reported in the “Ethic self-assessment” – Annex 5 – at the end of Annex 3.

No biological resources, subject to Access and Benefit Sharing (Nagoya Protocol) Regulations (Regulation (EU) No.511/2014; Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1866) will be used in the EOM4Soil project.

1.1.8. Publications & authorships policy

During the 24th October 2024 last meeting, coordinators and all participants agreed on following rules about publications and authorships:

- Each WP leader (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7) will manage one overall WP publication. Anyway, authorship list will be generated in function of the article objectives, contents and used datasets. Anyway, coordinator and co-coordinator should check/revise the publications before submitting them.
- In EOM4Soil, WPs interactions exist: therefore, the crossing exploitation of multiple datasets/variables/indicators deriving from different WP activity will generate co-authorship automatically.

In addition, with reference to EJPSOIL Grant Agreement:

"Data management, formalized in Data Management Plan (WP1, D1.4), will be based upon the H2020 guidelines on FAIR data management and the H2020 open access policy for dissemination. This will consider the property rights of the data collected and shared and the need of anonymization for surveys or online consultations and in accordance with the property rights and the rules agreed for backgrounds in the Consortium Agreement and will follow art. 29.3 of the GA."

1.1.8.1 Using databases

Supplying part of an EOM4Soil database for publishing does not mean the automatic authorship in the publication, since the authorship requests the partial writing or the critical review/implementation of the article.

IMPORTANT: Every partner using a database to publish but generated by another partner, must anyway inform the owners and invite them to participate. Partners interested in actively participating to article writing are welcome.

Besse et al., (2022). Guidance to data/metadata/datasets expectations, open access publications & reporting.
<https://youtu.be/NNmQC65d3c>

1.1.8.2. Budget

EOM4Soil budget for opensource publications must comply with those reported in the project proposal and extra-budget proposal (→ "Deliverables" → "Other costs" by each partner).

Potential publication fees for non-planned open-source publications, coherent with the project objectives and of high quality, should be covered by the author institution subscriptions, independently from EOM4Soil budget.

